

FATIGUE DAMAGE CHARACTERIZATION IN SHORT GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYAMIDE-66

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Abstract

This paper aims at studying the fatigue damage behavior of injection molded 30%wt-short glass fiber reinforced polyamide-66 composite (PA66/GF30). The dynamic modulus, cyclic creep and temperature field evolutions during fatigue testing were analyzed. Post-mortem 3D damage analysis by X-Ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) of PA66/GF30 were performed to further understand the damage mechanisms during fatigue loading. Results show that the information of dynamic modulus, strain and temperature evolution are important to evaluate the damage evolution. The μ CT analysis allows damage mechanisms reconstruction.

1 General Introduction

The reduction of vehicle mass is a major concern for automotive industries to comply with the strict pollution regulation, particularly for the CO₂ emission. Fiber reinforced thermoplastic materials are good candidates to provide the required lightweight properties but their structural durability has not yet been fully investigated. In particular further study to comprehend the fatigue damage behavior of these composites is necessary.

Various techniques have been used to evaluate the damage in short fiber reinforced composites. Early works of Horst et. al. [1, 2] performed fractography analysis onto the fracture surface of fatigued specimens by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and they proposed a damage mechanisms scenario which consider that the damage is initialized at fiber ends due to fiber-matrix debonding. The evolution of dynamic modulus, i.e. the slope of stress-strain hysteresis curve, has been proposed by several authors to evaluate the level of damage of the

composites [3–8]. Since the damage process is thermally activated, thermography technique by using infra-red camera has become an important tool for fatigue damage evaluation in composites [9–14]. Due to the 3D distribution of damage in such materials, tomography technique has become a suitable tool for fatigue damage characterization in composites [15–17].

During fatigue loading of the composite, some physical phenomena can develop concurrently, such as the damage, cyclic creep and increase of temperature that all can participate to the overall fatigue strength of the material [1, 18, 19]. A comprehensive study of fatigue damage behavior is necessarily being coupled by the analysis of all interrelating phenomena during fatigue loading.

The objective of this work is to characterize the fatigue damage mechanisms of PA66/GF30. It is proposed to use the analyses of dynamic modulus, cyclic creep and temperature field evolutions during fatigue testing together with post-mortem 3D damage analysis by X-Ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) to further understand the damage mechanisms during fatigue testing. To evaluate the anisotropic property of PA66/GF30 due the skin-shell-core structure produced by injection molding process [20–22], two specimen directions longitudinal and transverse to the mold flow direction (MFD) are examined.

2 Experimental Methods

2.1 Material

The material studied is an injection molded 30%wt of short glass fiber reinforced polyamide-6,6 composites (PA66/GF30) provided by Solvay Engineering Plastics-France. The material is

presented in the form of rectangular plate with a thickness of 3.2 mm. This material has a specific microstructure characterized by a skin-shell-core structure, typical of thermoplastic composites manufactured by injection molding process [20, 21, 23].

X-ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) technique was employed to study the microstructure (fiber orientation) of PA66/GF30. The μ CT experiment was carried out at ID19 beam line of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) Grenoble, France [24]. A voxel resolution of $1.4\mu\text{m}$ was achieved by the experimental setup. The μ CT experiment was performed on the sample with dimension of $2 \times 2 \times 3.2 \text{ mm}^3$ that has been extracted from the unloaded (virgin) specimen. By the current experimental setup, the thickness scanning was limited to 2.8 mm so that the final analyzed volume was $2 \times 2 \times 2.8 \text{ mm}^3$.

The microstructure of PA66/GF30 is shown in Fig. 1. The ImageJ freeware was used to visualize the microstructure. As described in Fig. 1, around 90% of fibers are located at the shell layer with a global fiber orientation longitudinal to the mold flow direction (MFD). The core layer represents about 5% of fiber content with a global fiber orientation perpendicular to the MFD. A random skin layer is formed at the area in direct contact to the mold surface. The thickness of the skin layer represents about 5% of fiber content, considering both the upper and lower skin layers. Although the random skin layer was developed, the fibers in this layer seemed to have tendency to orient to the MFD. The quantitative analysis of the degree of randomness will be addressed in our next work. The formation of skin-shell-core layer was only developed through the thickness of the material and no microstructure heterogeneity was found through the width and length of the specimen.

Mostly, the fibers orient parallel to the shear flow direction. The shear flow exists at the zone near to the wall due to the friction between the polymer melt and mold wall, whereas the shear flow is zero in the core zone due to the absence of mold wall friction influence. This leads fibers to orient parallel to MFD at the shell zone and perpendicular to MFD at the core zone. A thin random layers were formed due to

the polymer melt that is in direct contact with the relatively cold temperature of the mold wall and hence fibers freeze without any preferential orientations [20].

The μ CT 3D image segmentation of the fiber via gray value thresholding was carried out to allow calculation of fiber dimensions. Avizo and Visilog softwares were used for this purpose. Based on the computation result, the fiber average diameter and length after the injection molding process were 10 and $270 \mu\text{m}$, respectively.

Several virgin samples have been observed by μ CT analysis and it was shown that no visible damage is observed inside the sample which confirms that the initial damage due to the manufacturing process is negligible.

2.2 Specimens

Specimens used for mechanical characterizations were machined from the rectangular plate produced by injection molding process. The specimens were machined longitudinally and transversely to the MFD, defined hereafter as the longitudinal and transverse specimens. The description of longitudinal and transverse specimens, as well as its main dimensions are illustrated in Fig. 2.

2.3 Experimental procedures

Tensile and fatigue tests were performed on dry as mold PA66/GF30 ($<0.2\%$ water content) at room temperature. Tensile tests were performed upon a servo-hydraulic machine at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min , which corresponds to the strain rate of $3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Fatigue tests were performed by applying sinusoidal wave, load controlled mode at constant amplitude. The frequency of 3Hz was chosen in order to avoid an excessive heating of the composites. Fatigue strength of the material was evaluated within the range of 10^3 to 10^6 cycles. Fatigue tests were stopped if the specimens didn't reach final fracture at 5×10^5 cycles. To prevent specimens from buckling, the tests were conducted under tension-tension mode, with a stress ratio $R=0.1$. The data of cyclic creep and dynamic modulus evolution during fatigue loading were extracted from the servo-hydraulic machine acquisition software. Continuous temperature monitoring of the active zone of the specimen was

assured by the CEDIP Jade III MWR infrared camera with a spectral range between 3.9 and 4.5 μm . The μCT analyses were performed on the samples extracted from the virgin specimen and the longitudinal and transverse specimens after being subjected into fatigue loading till failure. The sample dimension and experimental procedures were similar to those for the microstructure analysis. The fatigue loaded samples for the μCT analysis were extracted far from the fracture surface. By segmentation technique with proper selection of threshold value, the voids inside the analyzed μCT volume element can be isolated, thereby the void properties such as volume, orientation angle and aspect ratio can be quantified. The Avizo and Visilog software were used for this purpose. In this work, the void aspect ratio and orientation angle in the shell and core representative volumes will be presented to confirm the damage mechanisms in PA66/GF30.

3 Results

3.1 Tensile behavior

The tensile properties of PA66/GF30 are described in Fig. 3. This figure illustrates the strong anisotropy effect induced by the injection molding process. The Young modulus and ultimate stress of the longitudinal specimen are twice than that of the transverse specimen. On the other hand, the ductility of the longitudinal specimen is half than that of the transverse specimen. The fiber orientations through the thickness of the specimen were predominantly occupied by the shell layer where the fibers are longitudinally oriented to the MFD. This yields the shell layer to dominantly govern the tensile behavior of PA66/GF30.

3.2 Macroscopic fatigue damage evaluation

Fig. 4 illustrates the evolution of the monitored parameters, i.e. normalized dynamic modulus (E_N/E_0), maximum strain (ϵ_{max}) and mean temperature ($T_{\text{mean}}-T_{\text{room}}$) for the longitudinal and transverse specimens. During cyclic loading, energy dissipation can be associated to different phenomena such as damage development and intrinsic dissipation (viscous behavior). Part of the energy dissipation due to the damage development and viscous effect of the material is turned into heat so

that thermal-viscous-damage coupling can occur during fatigue loading.

The loss of dynamic modulus can be used as a damage indicator when considering a classical damage mechanics framework. For all loading cases encountered in this study, the normalized dynamic modulus evolution showed a stable value for the first 10^3 cycles and then decreased more or less depending on the loading level. In all cases, the intensity of the normalized dynamic modulus drop was directly related to the fatigue life of the specimen.

The evolution of mean temperature exhibited two regimes. The first one corresponded to a stable normalized modulus, where heat dissipation seemed to be mostly related to the intrinsic energy dissipation associated to the viscous nature of the composite. The second regime was associated to the beginning of the normalized dynamic modulus drop and corresponded to an inflexion point on the mean temperature curve. This regime change can be associated to the fact that the energy dissipation was not fully dissipated into the heat due to the viscous nature of composite but also dissipated into a damage development.

In each cycle of a stress controlled fatigue test, stress-strain hysteresis loop is developed due to the viscous nature of the material. As the number of cycles increases, cyclic creep occurs, concerning to the phenomenon where the viscous effect is accumulated through the increase of overall material strain such as that of maximum or minimum strain. As shown in Fig. 4, the maximum strain continuously increased during fatigue life which demonstrates that cyclic creep occurred during fatigue loading. This also demonstrates that the fatigue energy was partly dissipated into the form of viscous dissipation. While the viscous dissipation was observed, no particular regime change was detected, except for the highest loading level of the transverse specimen ($\sigma_{\text{max}}=70\%\sigma_u$). One may consider that the fatigue energy dissipated into the form of viscous dissipation was weak and thus the dynamic modulus loss was more governed by the damage development.

The longitudinal and transverse specimens exhibited different behavior considering that the thermal-

viscous-damage coupling in longitudinal specimens was higher than that in transverse specimens. With the stress levels significantly lower than those in longitudinal specimens, the transverse specimens generated higher changes in dynamic modulus, strain and temperature. This is due to the fact that in transverse specimens, the polyamide matrix play more important role than that of fibers during the fatigue loading.

It can be summarized that the information of dynamic modulus is important though it becomes more difficult to completely comprehend the fatigue damage behavior without the information of strain and temperature evolution. The evolution of dynamic modulus is good as a damage indicator, though in high stress level it may overpredict the damage evolution due to the high viscous effect contribution of the composite, such as the one shown in the highest loading level of the transverse specimen. In the next subsection, the microscopic analysis of damage by μ CT method will be discussed in order to further comprehend the fatigue damage behavior in PA66/GF30.

3.3 Microscopic fatigue damage analysis

Based on visual observation of the μ CT 3D image, dark spots and dark line paths were noticed frequently, either situated along or between the fibers in the damage zone of the fatigue loaded specimens. Some small local changes of grey levels in the matrix were also detected, which could be due to the intrinsic artifact of μ CT image or due to the real matrix morphology or damage. By comparison to the virgin specimen, the presence of distinctive dark spots and dark line paths are believed to be associated to fatigue damage. The dark spot could be related to the void, whereas dark line path could be related to the interfacial debonding or matrix cracking.

Damage mechanisms of the fatigue loaded specimens were mainly located along fiber interface (Fig. 5b), though it is impossible to say if local damage was adhesive or cohesive. Fiber ends were found though it didn't necessarily involve in interfacial debonding (Fig. 5a). Despite the difficulty to present in 2D image, it was shown that initial damage appeared in locations where fibers are close to each other, especially in the region where fiber

fraction is locally higher. The damage then propagated and coalesced till the final failure. In a particular case, matrix transverse cracks can be developed, such as the one found in the core layer of the transverse specimen (Fig. 6). The relatively thin of core layer is believed to bear higher stress level due to its longitudinal orientation to the loading direction. Transverse cracks were found to develop favorably in this region.

The damage mechanisms were confirmed by evaluating the void aspect ratio vs. orientation of the μ CT volume element. The evaluation was carried out in every $50\mu\text{m}$ through the thickness of the μ CT image volume, thus it corresponds to the volume of $50 \times 2000 \times 2000 \mu\text{m}^3$ for each analysis. Consistent trend on void properties was found for all the examined volume of the samples. As shown in Fig. 7, voids with low aspect ratio were detected in the unloaded sample. Mostly the voids had very small volume. This trend was consistent for the skin, shell and core layers. The voids observed in the unloaded sample could be partly due to the real initial damage and partly due to the fluctuation of the grey scale. In longitudinal specimen, the majority of voids in the shell and core layers were oriented at 0° (longitudinal to MFD) and 90° (transverse to MFD), respectively (Fig. 8). These orientations are the same as the fiber orientations in the shell and core layers which mean that the voids, notably those with high aspect ratio are located along fiber interface in the form of interfacial debonding. The trend of the volume was the same as that of aspect ratio, which demonstrates that the void becomes higher in volume and elongates due to the fatigue loading. For the transverse specimen, the voids in the shell and core layers were both oriented at 90° (transverse to MFD), as shown in Fig. 9, which shows that interfacial debondings occurred in the shell layer while transverse crackings were found in the core layer of the composite. The random skin layer in the longitudinal and transverse specimens possessed the same behavior as that in shell layer. As discussed in the section of 2.1, even though the random skin layer was developed, the degree of randomness was not high and the fibers in this layer seemed to have tendency to orient to MFD, which is the same orientation as that in the shell layer.

4 Conclusions

The fatigue and damage behavior of PA66-GF30 have been studied. The information of dynamic modulus, strain and temperature evolution are important to evaluate the damage evolution. The information of dynamic modulus is important though it becomes more difficult to analyze unambiguously without the information of strain and temperature evolution. The evolution of dynamic modulus is good as a damage indicator, though in high stress level it may overpredict the damage evolution due to the high viscous effect contribution of the composite. The μ CT analysis allows damage mechanisms reconstruction. The initial damage appears in locations where fibers are close to each other, especially in the region where fiber fraction is locally higher. The damage then propagates through fiber interface and coalesces each other till the final failure. If the local stress distribution is high, the damage may propagate in the form of transverse cracks, such as the one observed in the core layer of the transverse specimen.

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Fig. 1 Skin-shell-core formation in PA66/GF30 which shows preferential orientation of fibers randomly, longitudinally (L) and transversely (T) to the mold flow direction (MFD) for skin, shell and core layers, respectively

Fig. 2 The description of longitudinal and transverse specimens of PA66/GF30

Fig. 3 The tensile properties of longitudinal and transverse specimens of PA66/GF30

Fig. 4. The evolution of normalized dynamic modulus (E_N/E_0), maximum strain (ϵ_{max}) and mean temperature ($T_{mean}-T_{room}$) for (a) longitudinal and (b) transverse specimens during fatigue loading. The σ_u represents the ultimate tensile strength value of its respective specimen orientation angles.

Fig. 5. Void at fiber ends (a) and interfacial debonding (b) observed in the shell zone of longitudinal specimen

Fig. 8. General trend of void aspect ratio vs. theta angle in the shell and core zones of longitudinal specimen

Fig. 6. Transverse crack observed in the core zone of transverse specimen

Fig. 9. General trend of void aspect ratio vs. theta angle in the shell and core zones of transverse specimen

Fig. 7. General trend of void aspect ratio vs. theta angle in the unloaded specimen